

Community Perception of Wounds and Health Seeking Behaviors amongst Youths in an Urban Setting in Cameroon.

Mboni Loveline Gam^{1*} Loveline Lum Niba², Bi Suh Mary Atanga³,

¹Department of Public Health, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Bamenda, Bamenda- Cameroon.

Email: lumnyanga@gmail.com

²Department of Public Health, Faculty of Health Sciences, The University of Bamenda, P.O. Box 39, Bambili, Bamenda- Cameroon Email: lovelinemboni@yahoo.com

³Department of Nursing and Midwifery, Faculty of Health Sciences, The University of Bamenda, PO Box 39, Bamenda-Cameroon. Email: maryatanga@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Background: A wound is defined as a defect or break in the continuity of the skin that results from physical mechanical or thermal damage, or that develops as a result of the presence of an underlying medical or physiological disorder. In the young age group of 15–29 years, five of the 15 leading causes of death are related to unintentional injury.

Objective: This study was aimed at assessing the community perception on wounds and health seeking behaviours among youths in the Nkwen Health area, Bamenda, North West Region of Cameroon.

Materials and Methods:

This study was a community-based cross-sectional study involving 59 females and 84 males with a mean age of 29.5±6.3years. Participants were randomly enrolled for a period of two months. Youths 18 to 35 years (59 females and 84 males) who had ever sustained a wound and who accepted to take part were included in the study. A questionnaire was used to collect data. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 23 and presented using frequency distribution tables and charts. Cross tabulations were used to assess association between categorical variables.

Results: Of the 143, 68.9% of youths had good perception of wounds and wound management. There was no significant association between perception and socio-demographic factors.

More than half (65%) of the youths have poor health seeking behaviours as they reported to first managed their wounds out of the hospital. There was a significant association between occupation and health seeking behaviour ($X^2 = 30.2, p = 0.001$). For reasons for choice, 71.1% shun the hospital due to high cost. There was a significant association between age category and cost as well as age category and fear of stigmatization ($X^2 = 7.34, p = 0.007$).

Conclusion: Youths in the Nkwen health area have a good perception on wounds and wound management but poor health seeking behaviours. High cost of conventional medicine is the main reason why they seek health care out of the hospital. Emphasis should be laid on the importance of seeking wound care at the hospital as early as possible after sustaining a wound.

Key words; *Wounds, Youths, Perception, Management, Health seeking behaviours, reasons.*

1.0. Background

Wounds are becoming a silent public health epidemic that affects a large fraction of communities in developing countries and people are more likely to suffer from different types of wounds throughout life [1]. Globally, it is estimated that 1.5% of people develop a wound at any one time [2]. Moreover, more than 90% of deaths resulting from unintentional injuries occur in low and middle countries [3]. The management of wounds remain a challenging clinical and public health problem, with early and late complications presenting a frequent cause of morbidity and mortality [4]. Evidence has demonstrated that a lack of wound care knowledge and skills negatively affects the prognosis of wounds. However, the use of health information technology positively affects prognosis [5]. Moreover, in most communities in Africa, socio-cultural practices and beliefs usually influence wound care and health seeking behaviour amongst patients with wounds. In addition, most wounds are attributed to unperformed rituals or calamities and therefore require the attention of a traditional healer for its management. The experience of living with a chronic wound has a huge impact on a patient's quality of life. One of the most consistent findings is that pain is one of the symptoms that youths find most distressing [2, 3, 4].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO)'s Global Burden of Disease Study [6], 3.9 million deaths in 2004 were accounted for by unintentional injuries. The authors also reported that unintentional injuries are amongst the five leading causes of death amongst people 15–29 years. Evidence has demonstrated that 25% to 50% of hospital beds are occupied by patients with a wound, amongst which about 55% are either non-healing wounds, infected surgical wounds, pressure ulcers and leg/foot ulcers, gun-shot wounds and blast injuries [2]. The impact of wounds represents social, personal, financial and psychological costs on the individual and further economic drain on the health-care system.

The highest rates of wartime injuries occurred in Africa, where war-related deaths numbered 32 per 100,000 people [7]. Cameroon has an injury mortality rate of 102 people per 100,000 population that is over three times that of the African continent [8].

Healthcare seeking behaviour is the actions individuals take when they perceive themselves to have a health problem or to be ill for the purpose of finding an appropriate remedy [9]. Healthcare seeking behaviour is preceded by a decision-making process that is further governed by individuals and/or household community norms, religious beliefs and expectations as well as provider related characteristics and conduct [10]. Furthermore, wound care in the community is an unskilful practice that people perform in their homes and its often influenced by beliefs in traditional medicine [11]. The determinants of healthcare seeking behaviour include the nature of the wound nearness to a health facility, cultural beliefs, age, gender and socioeconomic, cost and perceived quality of care and drugs [10].

A study by Pieper *et al.* [12] in 2007 found that 38.2% and 58.7% of patients returning from hospitals did not know how to change their dressing at home or how to clean the wounds, respectively and resulted to alternative wound care practices as a result of lack of finances [12]. This may lead to poor management of the wound leading to infection in 3% to 15% of cases [13, 14].

Youths' perception of wounds influences their health-seeking behaviours. Thus, understanding their perception will help in policymakers to come out with more appropriate approaches in improving health seeking for those with wounds in this vulnerable population thereby reducing complications from delayed health seeking. Timely and appropriate treatment of wounds can help reduce wound-related morbidity and mortality. This study therefore set out to investigate community perception of wounds and to explore the health seeking behaviours amongst youths in the Nkwen Health Area, in the North West Region of Cameroon.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study participants

This study was a community-based cross-sectional study involving 143 youth (59 females and 84 males) aged 18 to 35 years who had sustained a wound and experienced community wound care residing in the Nkwen Health Area in the North West Region of Cameroon conducted between March and June 2022. Participants were selected using a convenient sampling technique.

2.2. Ethical considerations.

Approval to carry out this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Faculty of Health Sciences of the University of Bamenda (Include ur cleanace Reference here). Administrative clearance was obtained from the Regional Delegation of Public Health of the (Ref. N° 203/ATT/NW/RDPH/BRIGAD of 25 May 2022). Written informed consent and verbal consent were obtained from all participants and quarter heads respectively, before any data collection procedure commenced.

3.0.Data collection

3.1.Questionnaire

Data for this study was collected using a self-administered structured questionnaire which was piloted on 10 youths where? to ascertain the validity of the questionnaire. Data was collected at home between 9am and 1:00pm. The questionnaire which was made up of 25 questions had the following sections: a) Sociodemographic characteristics that included; age, gender, marital status, level of education, religion and occupation; b) Perceptions of youths on wounds and wound management which included; nutrition for wound healing, hygiene and youth impression on wound management in the hospital versus the use of herbal medicine; c) Health seeking behaviour of youths; the type of wound sustained, first steps taken when they sustain a wound, place of wound treatment and reasons for delay for seeking wound care; d) Reasons for choice of place/methods for seeking wound care; which included reasons for seeking wound care strictly in the hospital, out of the hospital and reasons for using both hospital and herbal medicine.

The section on perception of wounds and wound management consisted of 20 questions and participants were assessed based on the number of times they responded "yes" to the questions. Out of the 20 questions, a participant was considered to have good perception of wounds and wound healing when he had a score of 15 out of the 20 questions.

3.2. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS for Windows version 23.0. Patients' sociodemographic characteristics and perception of wounds were presented using frequency distribution tables and charts. Association between youth perception of wounds and some selected sociodemographic variables was assessed using Chi square test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

4.0.RESULTS

4.1.Descriptive characteristics of the study population

This study included 143 participants (mean age 26.5 ± 5.3 years). Table 1 shows the descriptive characteristics of the study participants. A majority of the youths (69.9%) were in the age group 28 – 35 years, 54.5% were married and 9.1% had no formal education.

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of study participants (N=143)

VARIABLE	Frequency	Percentage	Mean±SD
Gender			
Female	59	41.3	26.5± 5.3
Male	84	58.7	
Age categories (years)			
18-27 years	43	30.1	
28-35 years	100	69.9	
Marital status			
Single	52	36.4	
Married	78	54.5	
Divorced	3	2.1	
Widowed	10	7.0	
Educational level			
No formal education	13	9.1	
Primary	35	24.5	
Secondary	59	41.3	
Tertiary	36	25.2	
Religion			
Christian	133	93.0	
Muslim	8	5.6	
Traditionalist	2	1.4	
Occupation			
Trader	38	26.6	
Civil servant	14	9.8	
Professional	37	25.9	
Student	29	20.3	
Farmer	25	17.5	

4.2. Youth perception of wounds and wound management

There was an overall perception of 68.9% among the youths. The overall percentage was gotten from the average of the sum total of the responses that captured good perceptions such as good nutrition being necessary for wound healing. Table 2 shows the perception of youths on wounds. We found that 79.0% reported that good nutrition was necessary for wound healing, while 83.9% of the youths reported hand washing was necessary before wound dressing, and two-thirds (60.1%) of the youths believed that a person cannot develop a wound if they walk or cross over a path where some ritual had been performed. However, less than 18% reported that seeking wound care out of the hospital was very effective. A majority (66.4%) reported that traditional ways of wound management can lead to complications.

Table 2: Youths perception on Wounds and wound management (N=143)

Perception	Frequency N	Percentage %
Good nutrition		
Necessary for wound healing	113	79
Not necessary for wound healing	5	3.5
No knowledge	25	17.5
Washing of hand before wound dressing		
Necessary	120	83.9
Not necessary	9	6.4
No knowledge	14	10
Perception of wound management		
Very effective	25	17.8
Effective	25	17.8
No great improvement	75	52.4
I do not know	18	12.5

We found no significant association ($p>0.05$) between some selected sociodemographic factors and youth perception of wounds. However, a higher proportion of females (89.7%) reported

Table 3: Association between demographic factors and Youths perception on Wounds and wound management (N=143)

VARIABLE	Yes n(%)	No n(%)	I do not know n(%)	X²	p*-value
Sex					
Female	52(89.7)	4(6.9)	2(3.4)	4.7	0.09
Male	65(79.3)	5(6.1)	12(14.6)		
Age group/years					
18-27	36(85.7)	1(2.4)	5(11.9)	1.78	0.4
28-35	81(82.7)	8(8.2)	9(9.2)		
Level of education					
No formal education	10(76.9)	1(7.7)	2(15.4)	3.98	0.7
Primary	26(76.5)	4(11.8)	4(11.8)		
Secondary	52(88.1)	3(5.1)	4(6.8)		
Tertiary	29(85.3)	1(2.9)	4(11.8)		
Occupation					
Trader	29(76.3)	4(10.5)	5(13.2)	6.9	0.54
Civil servant	9(69.2)	1(7.7)	3(23.1)		
Professional	33(91.7)	1(2.8)	2(5.6)		
Student	26(89.7)	1(3.4)	2(6.9)		
Farmer	20(83.3)	2(8.3)	2(8.3)		

4.3. Health seeking behavior amongst youth with wounds

We found that 42.4% of our study participants had sustained a wound through an accident, 11% in the field and 33.1% at home respectively. while 5.1% had incurred the wound at work. With regards to who recommended alternative sources for treatment, 59.1% of our participants reported a friend or family member while 3.65 reported a health practitioner. This can be seen on table 4.

Table 4: Health seeking behavior of youths on wounds (N= 143)

Variables	Frequency N	Percentage %
Person who recommended other sources of treatment		
Family and friend	65	59.1
Health practitioner	4	3.6
Self-recommendation	41	37.3
Reasons for delay in seeking care		
Hope to get over it without treatment	37	37.0
Lack of finances	37	37.0
Distance	15	15.0
Long awaiting time at the place of care	11	11.0
How to tell your wound is getting worst		
I perceive the odour	14	11.5
Pain increase	68	55.7
I feel feverish	3	2.5
Wound drainage increase	11	9.0
All of the above	17	13.9
I don't know	9	7.4
What was the outcome of your wound		
Healed	25	17.7
Became infected	38	27.0
Led to loss of body parts	2	1.4
Still healing	76	53.9

With respect to reasons for choice of seeking wound care out of the Hospital, the most cited reasons were high cost of conventional medicine (71.1%), accessible and available of other sources of treatment (69.4%), fear of stigmatization and pain (50.0%), cultural beliefs (58.2%) and advice from friends and relatives (63.3%). Figure 1 shows the reasons reported by the study participants for seeking wound care out of the hospital.

Figure 1: Study participant’s reasons for choosing to seek wound care out of the hospital setting.

5.0.DISCUSSION

This study noticed that out of a population of 143 participant's majority were males accounting for 58.7% while females made up 41.3%, this could be due to the fact that males engage in more risky tasks that cause wounds than females. This result is similar to that of Catherine et al in Yaoundé Cameroon who had 71% males [5]. However, the results differ from that of Haifaa *et al* [13] in Riyadh Region of Saudi who had more females (64.6%) than males (35.4%), this difference could be due to difference in sample size and difference in geographical area. Majority of the participants were in the age group 28 – 35years (69.9%) while a minority was in the age group 18 – 27 years (30.1%). The mean age was 29.5years. This is similar to that of Catherine et al in Yaoundé Cameroon who had a mean age of 29years [5]. The results differ from that of Haifaa et al in Riyadh Region of Saudi who had a mean age of 33.6years; this could be due to the focus on youths whereas the research in Saudi was focused on adults 18 to 75years. 36.4% of the participants were married; this is different from Haifaa *et al* who had 50.0% married. This difference is due to the population sampled which was mainly on youths.

Out of the 143 participants, 113(79.0%) think good nutrition is necessary for wound healing, similar results obtained by Haifaa *et al* in Saudi who reported 91% of participants affirming that nutrition is necessary for wound healing. 83.9% of the youths think hand washing is necessary before wound dressing which is similar to Haifaa *et al* in Saudi who sampled 371 youths out of whom 332 (89.6%) believed that hands should be washed before changing wound dressing. Out of the 143 sampled in this study 86 (60.1%) of the youths believe that a person cannot develop a wound if they walk or cross over a path where some ritual has been performed, this high perception could be likened to the advancement of the African man who in the past used to believe in no natural cause of an ailment unless proven otherwise. Of the total participants, 52.4% reported that wound management out of hospital is not effective. These findings differ from TL Calhoun who outlined that, injuries sustained by youths lead to extensive rehabilitation processes often overshadowed by the youth's perceptions of discrimination and mistrust in medical staff [14]. Most of the youths (66.4%) think traditional ways of wound management can lead to condition that is more chronic, these results are similar to those of Haifaa *et al* [13] where only 16.9% of youths did not think that using Zamzam water (a traditional practice) to wash wounds may shorten the recovery time. Overall, 68.9% of participants have good perception on wound and wound management. More females (89.7%) than males (79.3%) think a person can develop a wound if they walk or cross over a path where some ritual was performed, this was however not statistically significant ($X^2 = 4.7, p = 0.09$). The age group 18 – 27 years reported more than the age group 28 – 35 years (85.7% versus 82.7%) that crossing a ritual path could lead to a wound with no significant difference ($X^2 = 1.78, p = 0.4$). For education, those at the secondary level (88.1%), tertiary (85.3%) reported a little more than those primary level (76.5%) and those with no formal education (76.9%), these slight differences were however not statistically significant ($X^2 = 3.98, p = 0.7$). Also, there was no significant difference between occupation and perception ($X^2 = 6.9, p = 0.54$).

As for where the patients treat their wounds, 50 (35.0%) reported that they do at the hospital, 48 (33.6%) manage with herbs at home and 45(31.5%) with traditional healers. 38.6% use both hospital and other sources for wound management however, only 26.7% said the hospital is aware of their use of multiple sources for wound management. These are similar to those obtained by Biswas et al who had majority practicing local wound care and mostly by using traditional healers [15].

For the association between gender and health seeking behaviors, more males 27.4% than females 27.1% take wounds to hospital. Concerning seeking traditional healing, 13.6% of females and more males, 22.6% take wounds to traditional healers. Comparing females to males for self-management, more females, 59.3% manage wounds at home while 50.0% of males manage at home. Despite the differences in male and female preferences, there was however, no statistically significant difference between gender and health seeking behaviors ($X^2 = 2.1, p = 0.36$), these results differ from those obtained by Kennedy et al who reported the proportion of female adolescents seeking healthcare in the doctor's practice being significantly higher than for males [16].

Out of those 18-27years, 14.0% take wound to hospital while 33.0% of those 28-35 years take wounds to hospital, these results are similar to those of Oberoi *et al* [17] who found out that respondents from older age groups reported seeking care from government health facilities more often compared to those from younger age groups[17]. For preference of traditional healing, 20.9% of those 18-27 years take to traditional healers while 18.0% of those 28-35years take to traditional healers. A greater percentage (65.1%) of those 18-27 years manage wounds on their own compared to 49.0% of those 28-35 years. There was no statistically significant association between age group and health seeking behaviors ($X^2 = 5.6, p = 0.06$). These results are similar to those of Oberoi *et al* [17] whose results revealed no statistical significance between socio demographic factors and seeking care from traditional/herbal practitioners[17]

A greater percentage (34.6%) of those who were married take wounds to the hospital compared to only 21.2% of singles and 10.0% those who are widowed. Comparatively majority of those who are widowed (20.0%) rather take to traditional healers, followed by singles (19.2%) compared to only 16.7% of those who are married. Consistently, the widowed prefer to manage their wounds at home (70.0%), followed by the singles (59.6%), 48.7% of those who are married, and only 33.3% of divorced. However, these differences were not statistically significant ($X^2 = 9.4, p = 0.15$). For educational level, a greater percentage (34.3%) of those who had attained primary level of education take wounds to hospital compared to 27.8% of those who had attained tertiary education, 23.7% of those who had attained secondary education and 23.1% of those with no formal education. Consistently, those at primary level of education are the highest in seeking traditional healing (28.6%), followed by those with no formal education (23.1%), those at the secondary level of education (18.6%) and then tertiary (8.3%). A majority (63.9%) of those at tertiary level of education manage wounds on their own, followed by those at the secondary level (57.6), those with no formal education (53.8%) and then those at the primary level of education (37.1%). There was no statistically significant association between educational level and health seeking behaviors

($X^2 = 7.6, p=0.27$), these findings are similar to those reported by Haifaa *et al* [13] whose findings revealed a gap between the level of education and knowledge and beliefs which could negatively affect clinical outcomes [13]. More Muslims (50.0%) than Christians (26.3%) take wounds to hospital while 50% of traditional healers, 25% of Muslims and 18% of Christians take wounds to traditional healers. Comparatively, more Christians (55.6%) manage wounds on their own while 50.0% of traditionalists manage on their own and 25.0% of Muslims manage on their own. There was however no statistically significant association between religion and health seeking behaviors ($X^2 = 4.7, p=0.32$). These results differ from those obtained by Bushra *et al* [18] In Norway who found an association between Muslim religiosity and positive health outcomes [18] Also, Isaac *et al.*, [19]. reported a significant influence of cultural belief systems on health seeking behaviours [19]. For those who take wounds to the hospital, majority were Professionals (48.6%), followed by civil servants (28.6%), farmers (24.0%), students (17.2%) and traders (15.8%). Meanwhile for those who take wounds to traditional healers, majority were traders (39.5%), followed by farmers (24.0%), students (13.8%), civil servants (7.1%) and Professionals (2.7%). Comparatively, students constituted the majority who prefer to manage on their own (69.0%), followed by civil servants (64.3%), farmers (52.0%), Professionals (48.6%) and traders (44.7%). There was a statistically significant association between occupation and health seeking behaviors ($\chi^2 = 26.9, p=0.001$). These findings are similar to those obtained by Tinzar *et al* [20] in Thailand who had a positive association between occupation and health seeking behaviours [20].

This study identified the majority of the participants (71.1%) seek care out of the hospital due to high cost of conventional medicine. 69.4% said their choice of place for seeking wound care out of hospital was because other sources were accessible and available, 50.0% for fear of stigmatization and pain, 58.2% because of cultural beliefs, 44.9% due attitude of healthcare workers and 63.3% seek wound care out of hospital as result of advice from friends and relatives. These results are similar to those of Angkiatumjai *et al* [21] who reported the use of complementary and alternative medicine to be associated to the traditional beliefs [21]. This could be attributed to the fact that for most alternative treatment payment for treatment depends on its efficacy whereby the herbalist does not request for payment until after recovery.

For association between reasons for choice of seeking health care out of the hospital, there was a statistically significant relationship between gender and high cost of conventional medicine ($X^2 = 4.57, p=0.03$) with more males (78.7%) than females (58.3%). There was also a significant association between gender and fear of stigmatization, more males (60.7%) than females (32.4%) reported to seek health care out of the hospital due to stigmatization ($X^2 = 7.34, p=0.007$). Another significant association was observed between age group and cultural beliefs, and between occupation and cultural beliefs, the elderly age group 28-35years seek health care out of the hospital due to cultural beliefs more than the younger age group, ($X^2 = 7.2, p=0.007$). For occupation, traders (71%) and farmers (73.7%) reported that they seek health care out of the hospital due to cultural beliefs more than professionals (56.3%), civil servants (55.6%) and students (30.4%), this was statistically significant ($X^2 = 11.3, p=0.02$).

For attitude of health care provider, there was a significant association with age group and occupation, the elderly age group seek health care out of the hospital than the younger age group (52.3% versus 30.3%), ($X^2 = 4.3, p=0.04$). For occupation, traders (67.7%), civil servants (66.7%) and farmers (52.6) reported to seek health care out of the hospital due to attitude of health care workers than professionals (25%) and students (13%), ($X^2 = 20.7, p<0.001$).

There was no significant association between age groups and level of education as well as advice from friends and relatives. For occupation, more traders (83.9%), farmers (68.4%), and professionals (56.3%) reported to seek health care out of the hospital because they received advice from friends and relatives than reported civil servants (44.4%) and students (43.5%).

CONCLUSION

The study found health seeking behavior of the youths to be poor; majority of them reported to have first managed their wounds with herbs at home as well as take to traditional healers, occupation was found to be significantly associated to health seeking behaviors. Therefore, youths in our setting need to be sensitized on the importance of seeking wound care in the hospital immediately after sustaining a wound to prevent complications from delayed health care seeking.

References

1. Komarcević A. Savremeni pristup tretmanu rana [The modern approach to wound treatment]. *Med Pregl*. 2000 Jul-Aug;53(7-8):363-8. Croatian. PMID: 11214479. Gottrup,
2. F., Henneberg, E., Trangbaek, R., Baekmark, N., Zollner, K. and Sorensen, J. (2013). Point prevalence of wounds and cost impact in the acute and community setting in Denmark. *J Wound Care*, 22, 413-4, 416, 418-22.
3. Nantulya V, Reich M (2002) The neglected epidemic: road traffic injuries in developing countries. *BMJ* 324:1139–1141
4. Natarajan S, Williamson D, Stiltz AJ, et al: Advances in wound care and healing technology. *Am J Clin Dermatol* 2000; 1: 269 –275. 2 Alonso JE, Lee J, Burgess AR, et al: The management of complex orthopaedic injuries. *Surg Clin North Am* 1996; 76: 879 – 903.3.
5. Kuan, T., Wang, F., Guo, Y., Tang, I., & Hou, C. (2020). Wound Care Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices and Mobile Health Technology Use in the Home Environment: Cross-Sectional Survey of Social Network Users. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.2196/15678>
6. Chandran, A., Hyder, A. A., & Peek-Asa, C. (2010). The Global Burden of Unintentional Injuries and an Agenda for Progress. *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 32(1), 110-120.
7. Bowman B, Seedat M, Duncan N, et al. Violence and Injuries. In: Jamison DT, Feachem RG, Makgoba MW, et al., editors. *Disease and Mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa*. 2nd edition. Washington (DC): The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank; 2006. Chapter 24. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK2308/>

8. Juillard C, Etoundi Mballa GA, Bilounga Ndongo C, Stevens KA, Hyder AA. Patterns of injury and violence in Yaoundé Cameroon: an analysis of hospital data. *World J Surg.* 2011 Jan;35(1):1-8. doi: 10.1007/s00268-010-0825-5. PMID: 21046382; PMCID: PMC7103103.
9. Ihaji E, Gerald EU, Ogwuche CH. Educational level, sex and church affiliation on health seeking behaviour among parishioners in Makurdi metropolis of Benue state. *JEPER* 2014;1:311-6
10. Oberoi, S., Chaudhary, N., Patnaik, S., & Singh, A. (2016). Understanding health seeking behavior. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 5(2), 463-464. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.192376>
11. Bhalla K, Harrison JE, Shahraz S, Fingerhut LA, Global Burden of Disease Injury Expert Group Availability and quality of cause-of-death data for estimating the global burden of injuries. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2010 Nov 01;88(11):831–838C. doi: 10.2471/BLT.09.068809.
12. Pieper B, Sieggreen M, Nordstrom CK, Freeland B, Kulwicki P, Frattaroli M, Sidor D, Palleschi MT, Burns J, Bednarski D. Discharge knowledge and concerns of patients going home with a wound. *J Wound Ostomy Continence Nurs.* 2007;34(3):245–253. doi: 10.1097/01.WON.0000270817.06942.00.
13. Quinn JV, Polevoi SK, Kohn MA. Traumatic lacerations: what are the risks for infection and has the 'golden period' of laceration care disappeared? *Emerg Med J.* 2014 Feb;31(2):96–100. doi: 10.1136/emered-2012-202143.
14. Pieper B. Vulnerable populations: considerations for wound care. *Ostomy Wound Manage.* 2009 May 01;55(5):24–37.
15. Franks PJ, Barker J, Collier M, Gethin G, Haesler E, Jawien A, Laeuchli S, Mosti G, Probst S, Weller C. Management of Patients with Venous Leg Ulcers: Challenges and Current Best Practice. *J Wound Care.* 2016 Jun;25 Suppl 6:S1-S67. doi: 10.12968/jowc.2016.25.Sup6.S1. PMID: 27292202 .
16. Catherine J., Etoundi Mballa GA, Bilounga Ndongo C, Stevens KA, Hyder AA. Patterns of injury and violence in Yaounde Cameroon: an analysis of hospital data. *World journal of surgery.* 2011 Jan;35(1):1-8.
17. Oberoi, S., Chaudhary, N., Patnaik, S., & Singh, A. (2016). Understanding health seeking behavior. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 5(2), 463-464. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.192376>
18. Tamara L Cahloun: Engaging with African American youth following gunshot wound trauma: the Calhoun cultural competency course. Boston University, 2019.
19. Biswas Animesh B., Abu S., Koustuv D., Toity D., Fazlur R., and Saidur R. Exploring perceptions of common practices immediately following burn injuries in rural communities of Bagladesh. *BMC Health Services research* (2018). 18:467.
20. Kennedy O., Janan D., Fatima L., Stefanie H., Busisiwe Nkala., Lucy C., Angela K., Glenda E. Gray, Cari L. Miller: Health-seeking behaviours by gender among adolescents in Soweto, South Africa. *Global Health Action* 2015. # 2015.

21. Kaamel M. Nuhu. Determinants of Health-Seeking Behavior in Ghana. Southern Illinois University Carbondale, March 2018.
22. Bushra Ishaq, Lars Ostby, and Asbjorn Johannessen. Muslim religiosity and health outcomes: A cross-sectional study among Muslims in Norway.
23. Isaac Acheampong. The power of Beliefs on Health Seeking Behaviour: Implication for Therapeutic Relationships for Cardiovascular care. *European Journal of Medicine* 10(4). DOI: 10.13187/ejm.2015.10.195
24. Tinzar N., Alan G., Petechawan P. Migrant workers occupation and healthcare-seeking preferences for TB-suspicious symptoms and other health problema; a survey among immigrant workers in Songkhla province, southern Thailand.
25. Angkiatkumjai, M., Boardman, H. & Walker, DM. Potential factors that influence usage of complementary and alternative medicine worldwide: a systematic review. *BMC Complement Med Ther* 20, 363 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-020-03157-2>
26. S. Meaume, J.C Kerihuel, I. Fromantinm L. Teot. Workload and prevalence of open wounds in the community: French Vulnus initiative. *Journal of wound of care*. Vol. 21, No.2. <https://doi.org/10.12968/jowc.2012.21.2.62>.
27. Nantulya V, Reich M (2002) The neglected epidemic: road traffic injuries in developing countries. *BMJ* 324:1139–1141
28. Kuan, T., Wang, F., Guo, Y., Tang, I., & Hou, C. (2020). Wound Care Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices and Mobile Health Technology Use in the Home Environment: Cross-Sectional Survey of Social Network Users. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.2196/15678>
29. Nherera and Treman. An Overview of Clinical and Health Economic Evidence Regarding Porcine Small Intestine Submucosa Extracellular Matrix in the Management of Chronic Wounds and Burns. *Wound&Management Prevention*. <https://www.hmpgloballearningnetwork.com/site/wmp/article/overview-clinical-and-health-economic-evidence-regarding-porcine-small-intestine-submucosa>

Data Availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in this publication.

Funding statement

This study was funded by the authors.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to all the youth that participated in our study

Received: 16 February 2025

Revised: 26 February 2025

Accepted: 4 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14963918>

Authors' contribution

LLN was responsible for the conception and design of the study, directed data collection and organization, statistical analysis and drafting of the manuscript. MLG contributed to the conception and design of the study, participated in data collection as well as interpretation and drafting of the manuscript. AMBS contributed to the conception and design of the study, participated in data collection, analysis of data and interpretation of data as well as drafting of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript for submission.